

Services Plan

Deliverable 3.1 Services Plan

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Description

Deliverable 3.1 Programme services document outlines all planned activities within the EmpoWomen Programme by offering the programme timeline with the sequence of programme events, detailed descriptions of the programme services, explains various session types, content, objectives, and outcomes.

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Table 1. Project information

PROJECT TITLE	Acceleration programme empowering women-led deep tech startups in Widening Area countries
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TASK LEADER/MAIN AUTHOR	Alona Belinska (SWG), Jenny Tooth (BAE)
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Table 2. History of Changes

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	03.04.2024	First draft of Programme services - SWG part	Alona Belinska (SWG)
v0.2	15.04.2024	Second draft of Programme services - SWG part	Alona Belinska (SWG)
v0.3	19.04.2024	Finalized draft of Programme services - SWG part	Alona Belinska (SWG)
v0.4	19.04.2024	Final review of the draft Programme services - SWG part	Ilze Graubina (SWG)
v0.5	23.04.2024	Document review	María Elena Martínez (Sploro)
v0.6	23.04.2024	Document update after SPLORO 1st review	Ilze Graubina (SWG)
v0.7	24.04.2024	Document update	Ilze Graubina (SWG)
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v0.9	28.04.2024	Part 2. Programme services	Jenny Tooth (BAE)
v1.0	29.04.2024	Document review	María Elena Martínez (Sploro)
v1.1	29.04.2024	Document review	Alona Belinska (SWG)
v1.2	30.04.2024	Document review	Alona Belinska (SWG)
v1.3	7.05.2024	Final document for review	Alona Belinska (SWG)
v1.4	10.05.2024	Document review	Alberto Sierra (SPLORO)

Table 3. Acronyms

Abbreviation	Full name	Description
SWG	Startup Wise Guys	Name of a legal entity
BAE	Business Angels Europe	Name of a legal entity
Q&A	Questions and answers	Session type
MVP	Minimum viable product	A version of a product with just enough features to be usable by early customers who can then provide feedback for future product development.
KPIs	Key performance indicators	Type of performance measurement.
1on1	One on one	Type of the session where the startup meets one expert
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats	SWOT analysis is a strategic planning and strategic management technique used to help a person or organization identify Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats related to business competition or project planning.
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation	The General Data Protection Regulation is a European Union regulation on information privacy in the European Union and the European Economic Area.
IP	Intellectual Property	Intellectual property is a category of property that includes intangible creations of the human intellect.

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1. Executive Summary

EmpoWOMEN is a 2-year programme (2024-2025) funded by the European Union through its Horizon Europe Research and Innovation program, aiming to tackle the underrepresentation of women in the deep-tech sector, particularly in emerging European countries. 25 selected via open calls women-led companies will participate in a unique acceleration programme, shaped together by StartupWiseGuys & BusinessAngelsEurope, and get services, awards and 45,000 euros in equity-free funding per startup.

There will be 2 cohorts, each cohort is a 6-month long programme designed for female-led deep-tech startups, to address the underrepresentation of women in the deep-tech sector and support them on their journey of building and scaling deep-tech startups.

This deliverable contains information about the EmpoWOMEN Acceleration Programme. Through a combination of mentorship, training workshops, networking events, and access to resources, the EmpoWOMEN Acceleration Programme, that will be lead by SWG with the support of BAE, equips participants with the skills, knowledge, and connections needed to thrive in the competitive business landscape.

2. Programme Overview

Programme starts on May 6th with a Welcome session and proceeds into working on startup KPIs and Goals for the programme and development of their deep tech startup.

First part of the programme is dedicated to working on different aspects of the startup journey such as problem definition, pitch presentation, sales, legal aspects, and fundraising. In the middle of the programme there will be a Progress Day event and KPIs and Goals check-in session in order to see how participants progressed during the first part of the programme.

After this participants will have several weeks of summer break and will come back to the second part of the programme in the beginning of September. Second part of the programme is dedicated to diving into topics related to fundraising and learning investments topics.

At the end of the programme, we plan to give a final Goals and settings session to assess startups development and invite startups to the Graduation event that will be held onsite.

Overview of the whole programme timeline with description of each part and main deliverables. i

Timeline

Programme timeline during 6 months

FIGURE. 1 Programme Timeline

3. Description of Programme Services

The EmpoWomen Programme offers a diverse range of services designed to empower and support participants in their journey. Through a collaborative effort between partners SWG and BAE, the programme delivers a comprehensive array of sessions and resources tailored to meet the needs of participants. Further is provided comprehensive and detailed explanations of programme services.

Our program is meticulously crafted to offer participants a multifaceted experience, divided into two distinct yet complementary parts. Together, these two parts form a comprehensive program that equips participants with practical skills and knowledge.

3.1 EmpoWOMEN programme PART 1

Part 1

First part of the programme will last 8 weeks - **How to build and scale women-led deep tech startup** led by Startup Wise Guys

FIGURE.2 Programme Part 1

The following table offers a succinct roadmap for the distribution of content over successive weeks. Each row represents a week, outlining the specific material or activities slated for delivery. This breakdown not only aids in scheduling but also provides a clear overview of the course or project's progression. As a reference point, the table serves as a guide for both mentors and participants, fostering effective communication and organization throughout the duration of the program or project.

Table 4 Programme by Week

WEEK	DESCRIPTION
WEEK 1 WELCOME WEEK	During this initial week, participants are encouraged to familiarize themselves with the programme's structure and objectives, tools, explore programme materials, and add the programme's event calendar to stay informed about upcoming online sessions. To stay connected and engage with fellow participants via Slack, where startups will find the latest updates and announcements.
WEEK 2 PURPOSE & VALUES	This week is about fundamental questions of the startup's purpose. To define a company's mission, vision, and culture, laying the groundwork for a clear understanding of entrepreneurial journey.

WEEK	DESCRIPTION
WEEK 3 PITCHING & PRODUCT	This week's purpose is to gain insights into effectively communicating the product and its value proposition. To emphasize the importance of understanding the problem each startup's product solves as the initial step toward successful sales and market penetration.
WEEK 4 PRODUCT & PLANNING	This week's focus is on refining the product to meet market demands and customer needs. To explore methods for experimentation and building or planning a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) to ensure it stands out and addresses key customer pain points.
WEEK 5 STAYING STRONG	This week's purpose is to navigate the challenges inherent in startup life by focusing on personal resilience and sustainable growth strategies. To identify methods to maintain peak performance and readiness to tackle obstacles as they arise.
WEEK 6 SALES	This week's purpose is to dive into an intensive crash course covering sales, marketing, and branding strategies. To channel efforts into refining sales approach while ensuring that the brand identity sets apart in the marketplace.
WEEK 7 FUNDRAISING	This week's purpose is to enhance the ability to communicate effectively with potential collaborators and investors. To explore financial metrics and strategies crucial for securing investment and scaling startups successfully.
WEEK 8 LEGAL BASICS AND PROGRESS DAY	This week's purpose is to address critical legal matters vital for a startup's compliance and protection. Topics include business registration, GDPR compliance, and strategies to mitigate legal risks. As well as having an online Progress Day to assess development of participant's mid programme.

3.1.1. Activities Overview

In this section, we delve into a comprehensive overview of the program activities facilitated by the SWG. Each week within the program is meticulously structured to encompass a variety of engaging elements aimed at fostering learning, collaboration, and growth among participating startups. The typical program week encompasses a blend of digital resources, interactive sessions, and personalised support mechanisms. This includes access to curated video materials and assignments via the Airtable platform, live Q&A sessions to address queries and concerns, peer-to-peer exchanges for collaborative learning, and one-on-one guidance from assigned Lead Coaches. These activities form the cornerstone of the program's dynamic and immersive learning environment, empowering startups to navigate challenges and capitalize on opportunities with confidence.

Moreover, beyond the regular cadence of activities, startups enrolled in the program are treated to additional enriching experiences designed to augment their journey towards success. These supplementary sessions encompass pivotal moments such as a warm welcome session at the onset of the program, where participants are introduced to the program structure and fellow cohorts, and a session dedicated to setting program goals and key performance indicators (KPIs), laying a solid foundation for focused progress. Furthermore, the program offers individual mentoring sessions tailored to address specific needs and aspirations of each startup, providing invaluable insights and guidance. Finally, the culmination of the program is marked by a celebratory graduation day held onsite, commemorating the achievements and milestones attained by the participating startups throughout their transformative journey with SWG.

Table 5 Programme Session Types

TYPE	DESCRIPTION	DURATION	PARTICIPANTS
Welcome session	Group session held in Zoom	1 or 1.5 hours	Startups, partners, moderator
Programme Goals & KPIs	Group session held in Zoom	1 or 1.5 hours	Startups, partners, moderator
Q&A	Group session held in Zoom	1.5 hours	Startups, moderator, expert
Peer to Peer	Participants are divided in small groups (3 to 5 startups) in the Zoom breakout rooms	1 hour	Startups, moderator
Webinar	Group session held in Zoom	1 or 1.5 hours	Startups, moderator, expert
Fireside chat	Group session held in Zoom	1 hour	Startups, moderator, expert
Pitch Drills	1on1 session held in Zoom, but any participant can attend as a listener	20 min per startup	Startup, moderator, expert
1on1 mentoring session	Individual mentoring session held in Zoom or Google Meets	Up to 60 min	Startup, mentor
Progress Day	Group session held in Zoom	1.5 - 2 hours	Startups, moderator, partners, external participants
Graduation Day	Onsite event	2 hours	Startups, moderator, partners, external participants

WEEK 1

Table 6 Weekly Overview – Week 1

ACTIVITY TYPE	WELCOME SESSION	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 1		
<p>This is the first session of the Programme. It is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead and invited Programme partners using the Zoom video call platform. The goal of this session is to welcome participants to the Programme, get to know each other, and explain the Programme rules and setup. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from the participants. After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the structure and rules of the Programme - how the Programme is organized, what activities are mandatory, etc. • Know how to navigate Programme tools and where to find information about sessions, etc. • What are the expectations of the Programme, main KPIs, and deliverables. • Get to know Programme partners and other Programme participants. 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME KPIS AND GOALS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG, Sploro, and BAE
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 1		
<p>This session is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead using Zoom video call platform. The goal of this session is to explain and remind to startups what the requirements of the Programme are. There are general objectives related to payments that all startups must fulfill. Additionally, KPIs and individual objectives will be defined with each startup. This session is 1-2h long depending on the number of questions from the participants. After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand why it is important to set goals and KPIs for their company; • Be reminded about Programme requirements to be included in their goals and KPIs. 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS “VOUCHER TO UNLOCK MENTORING”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 1		
<p>Each startup has a voucher to unlock individual mentoring in the amount of 16 individual mentoring sessions during the Programme. SWG has prepared the list of potential mentors and coaches that will be assigned to startups after beginning the Programme. These sessions will happen online between an assigned mentor and a specific startup. Each session is 30-60 min long depending on the number of questions from the startup. During these sessions, startups can focus on their deep tech business and</p>			

product development by consulting with mentors about various aspects of the business and technology, as well as discussing what was learned during the Programme and asking for suggestions.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PEER TO PEER SESSION “MYTHS AND STEREOTYPES” OF FEMALE-LED DEEP TECH STARTUPS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 1
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This session is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead using Zoom video call platform. The goal of this session is to give participants space to get to know other startups better, see what useful insights or contacts they can receive from others, and brainstorm together about relevant topics for female-led deep tech companies. All participants have access to the Peer-to-Peer session’s instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session’s topic. After the session, participants will:

- Learn the most popular stereotypes of female-led deep tech companies and how not to be discouraged by them.
- Discuss relevant life situations that happened with them or other women who are working on their deep tech business and how to overcome these obstacles.
- Get to know other participants better, build relationships and see how these contacts can be beneficial for building their business.
- Get motivated to move forward with building their deep tech business.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 1 “WELCOME AND GOALS SETTINGS” VIDEO MATERIALS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 1
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Week 1: This week is all about making sure that the startups have access to all the main information and tools to start the programme. Participants will have access to the Airtable platform with pre-recorded videos related to every week’s topic. These videos have a description of the topic of the week of the Programme, educational information about this topic, and a call to action in terms of suggestions on what tasks and templates to use and what actions to take. After viewing all the videos for the specific week, participants are required to complete the **Knowledge Check form**. This form includes questions related to the topics covered in the videos, allowing us to monitor participants' engagement and ensure they have watched the content.

Videos to watch:

- Welcome; 2 videos with an explanation of what this programme is about, timeline, every week’s topic.
- Problem solving mindset; tips and tricks on how to keep the mind open to explore problems from different perspectives.
- Mentoring Top 10 tips; tips on how to prepare for 1on1 meeting with coaches and mentors.

- Alumni Testimonials: inspirational talks from SWG Alumni about their experience with SWG and their startup journey that helps startups to stay encouraged.

After watching this week's videos participants will:

- Understand how the Programme works and where to find what information;
- Learn tips on how to work with mentors to get maximum benefit to their deep tech business;
- Listen to tips from Alumni Testimonials that went through similar Programmes before to understand how to better work with materials and mentors during the Programme;

Participants will have access to the Airtable platform with assignments related to every week's topic. This week's assignments are mandatory and are related to receiving access to the platform materials and providing important information to Programme organizers in order to fulfill the Programme requirements:

- Fill in the Startup Entry form; this is the first step to have startup information in the Database.
- Add Programme's calendar; this will ensure that startups will see in their calendar all the scheduled sessions and events.
- Join Slack; communication tool that will ensure that startups are up to date about upcoming activities and informed about other important events.
- Sign up to the Programme's Airtable to get access to the content; a place where the learning materials and information about the programme is available.
- Review the Goals and KPIs setting template; available on Airtable within the Week 1 learning material content.

WEEK 2

Table 7 Weekly Overview – Week 2

ACTIVITY TYPE	GOAL SETTING 1ON1 WITH LEAD COACH	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 2		
<p>This session is held online individually with every startup between participants from a specific startup and the Lead Coach using Zoom video call platform or Google Meets. The goal of these individual calls is to have dedicated time for every startup to talk about their personal, and company goals and KPIs in order to graduate from this Programme and also related to their business to achieve growth. This session is 30-60 min long depending on the number of questions from the participant.</p> <p>For the first session, a startup should have prepared a draft version to present it to the assigned lead coach. There will be organized follow-up sessions to check on goal setting process and at the end of the first programme month will be organized the last goal setting review session together with the BAE representative to present the final version and receive a confirmation from the lead coach and BAE representative that the goals are reasonable and achievable in the given time. After Goals and KPIs are</p>			

confirmed, the startup will receive the first funding of 5000 EUR. 1on1 individual sessions with the lead coach will continue after receiving the first funding to ensure that the goal achieving process is on track.

During these sessions, the startup will have a chance to ask any outstanding questions related to programme and startup goals, ask for help on how to define and set the goals as well as receive feedback.

Goals are required to be set for Part 1 and Part 2 for this programme, therefore the lead coach will be available up to 10 individual 1on1 sessions for 6 months.

After the session, participants will:

- Understand how to adapt the methodology of Goal setting to their particular use case.
- Set up Goals and KPIs for their deep tech startup business.
- Understand how to achieve the set goals.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 2 “PURPOSE AND VALUES” Q&A SESSION “SETTING GOALS”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 2
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This session is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead using the Zoom video call platform. The goal of this session is to explain to the participants how to work with Goal Setting template and how to set achievable, measurable, and reasonable goals for your startup.

All the participants have a chance to ask questions to prepare better for the first meeting with the assigned Lead coach who will work with a startup throughout the program ensuring that the startup is successfully reaching the set goals. This session is 2 hours. During the session, participants will:

- Learn the best practices on how deep-tech companies can set up their goals and KPIs and see examples of how other companies are setting goals and KPIs;

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 2 “PURPOSE AND VALUES” PEER TO PEER SESSION “PURPOSE AND VALUES FOR YOU AS FOUNDER OF A DEEP-TECH FEMALE LEAD STARTUP”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 2
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This session is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead using the Zoom video call platform. The goal of this session is to give participants opportunity to discuss Purpose and values of each startup and learn from others, as well as discuss related topics for female-led deep tech companies.

All the participants have access to the Peer-to-Peer session’s instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session’s topic. This session is 1 hour. After the session, participants will:

- Learn about personal and company values;

- Discuss how personal values affect company values and overall work performance;
- Think about setting their personal values and deep tech company values;

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 2 “PURPOSE AND VALUES” VIDEO MATERIALS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 2		

Week 2: This week is all about discovering the purpose, mission, vision, and culture of the company. An important part of this week is goal setting and introducing pitching. Participants will have access to the Airtable platform with pre-recorded videos related to every week's topic.

Videos to watch:

- Setting goals; educational information on how to identify achievable and reasonable Goals & KPIs
- Purpose and Values; educational information on how to identify purpose and values and align them with the goals.
- The power of strong culture; educational information on how to develop a strong culture and why it is important for a startup success.
- Team you are my army now; educational video with an explanation why it is important to identify the critical roles that should be filled in to set the startup for success and also revise the existing team and assigned roles to understand if the startup has right people in the team.
- Stages of startup; educational information about stages of startup and what actions should be taken to succeed.
- Deconstructing your business; educational information to help a startup understand better currently made business assumptions and how to capture the right value, for the right market segment, solving the right problems.
- Introduction to Pitching; educational information about different pitch types that a startup needs to know with practical advice on how to prepare a good pitch.

After watching this week's videos participants will understand:

- Goal Setting - how to set your Goals and KPIs;
- Purpose and Values - what is the importance of Purpose and values and how to align personal values with company values;
- The power of strong culture -how important is to build a culture in order to run your deep tech business and team;
- Team is my Army - how to build a strong team that can deliver results;
- Stages of A startup - what are stages of startups development and at what stage are you now with your deep tech startup;
- Deconstructing your business - how to deconstruct your business model to analyze if you are moving the right way;

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to pitching - how to do a 3-minute pitch; 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 2 “PURPOSE AND VALUES” ASSIGNMENTS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 2		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set goals for the Programme - finalize your Goals and KPIs; a template has been provided with instructions and some examples on how to set Business, Technology, Product, Raising investment, Sustainable (optional) goals along with mentorship plan. • What is your purpose - work on your personal and company purpose; document with exercise provided to help the startup founder understand the real purpose. • Your company's values - work on your personal and company values; template provided, and the startup is asked to fill it in with values and to ask the teammates to do the same to compile one list of the company values. • Lean Canvas exercise - create a Lean canvas for your deep tech business or review and update the existing one; template provided along with instructions and some hint questions to help a startup create a new version to see how they can optimize the business plan to maximize business value. • Start working on Pitch Deck - start working on your pitch deck for a 3-minute presentation or review and update the existing one; template provided to help startup create a solid 3-minute investor pitch deck. 			

WEEK 3

Table 8 Weekly Overview – Week 3

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 3 “PITCHING AND PRODUCT” Q&A SESSION “PROBLEM DEFINITION”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 3		
<p>This session is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead and Coach of the week using Zoom video call platform. The objective of this session is to review the startup's problem statement and assist in refining it to ensure it strongly aligns with product-market fit and resonates with potential clients. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from the participants. After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the problem definition techniques and why it is important; • Learn how to define if a problem is worth solving - if you can find market fit; 			

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn how to shape the definition of the problem to better target potential clients that have this problem; 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 3 PEER TO PEER SESSION “PITCH PRACTICE”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 3		
<p>This session is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead using Zoom video call platform. The goal of this session is to give participants the opportunity to practice their pitch with other startups this way they can get feedback from peers and also better understand what deep tech products other startups are building. All the participants have access to the Peer-to-Peer session’s instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session’s topic. This session is 1 hour long. After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get insights on what other startups are building and how they are presenting themselves; Practice presenting their pitch and receive feedback; 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 3 “PITCHING AND PRODUCT” VIDEO MATERIALS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 3		
<p>Week 3: This week's main focus is on how does startup’s product solves a real problem, a problem faced by its customers ensuring that the problem statement is rock-solid and resonates with customers.</p> <p>Videos to watch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Problems to solve; educational video helping startups to understand better how to create a solid problem statement. There are no problems, only solutions waiting to be found; educational video explaining how to unpack solution and test if it is the right one for the problem that a startup has identified. How to identify your ideal customer profile; educational video explaining how to identify types of companies that would buy a startup’s product and understand where they are getting similar services from. Powerful pitching; 4 educational videos about pitching techniques covering such topics as how to define a good hook, describe product, market, business, company. <p>After watching this week's videos participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn how to identify what problems are worth solving and look at them not as negative aspects but from the perspective of opportunity; Participants will learn methods on how to identify their ideal customer as this is one of the most important aspects in building the startup; 			

- Participants will have an introduction to “Powerful Pitching” module and will learn the structure of 3 min investor pitch and its elements as well as will see good pitch examples.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 3 “PITCHING AND PRODUCT” ASSIGNMENTS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 3		

This week's assignments are:

- Work on SWOT analysis to understand strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that their deep tech startup is facing; template provided to help a startup define SWOT.
- Work on defining the Ideal Customer Profile for their deep tech startup; template provided with questions to help startup to understand target audience and who are the potential paying customers.
- Start building their pitch deck or if they already have one assess if it corresponds to Programme requirements and industry standards; a document provided with instructions and questions to be answered that will help the startup to prepare an outstanding pitch deck.

WEEK 4

Table 9 Weekly Overview – Week 4

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 4 “PRODUCT AND PLANNING” Q&A SESSION “MVP AND PRODUCT BUILDING”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 4		

This session is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead and Coach of the week using Zoom video call platform. The objective of this session is to discuss MVP and Product building stages and answer participants' questions regarding this topic. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from the participants. After the session, participants will:

- Understand the stages of building MVP and Product;
- On what stage their deep tech startup currently is and how to move to the next one;
- Receive support from an experienced Technical person.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 4 “PRODUCT AND PLANNING” PEER TO PEER SESSION “TOUGH QUESTIONS”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 4		
<p>The goal of this session is to give participants an opportunity to discuss “tough questions” that every startup founder is facing on their journey, especially building a product in the deep tech industry. After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn how to effectively address tough questions and make difficult decisions because during the session there are asked questions to challenge every participant and think about different aspects of their business and personal values to prepare them for the next time when the same or similar question would be asked to have already prepared a solid answer; • Learn from each other how to address difficult question; • Be prepared to effectively address the challenging questions commonly asked by investors; 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 4 WEBINAR “WOMEN AND COMPLEX TECH SOLUTIONS”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 4		
<p>The goal of this session is to address and discuss what difficulties are facing women when building deep tech startups and other complex tech solutions, have role models speakers that can share positive examples, and discuss technological aspects of building deep tech products. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from participants.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive support on building their deep tech complex solutions; • Hear role models and positive examples of women building deep tech products; 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 4 “PRODUCT AND PLANNING” VIDEO MATERIALS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 4		
<p>Week 4: This week’s focus is on the product and making sure it is going to be something unique that the customers want. Videos to watch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing a value proposition; educational video explaining what a value proposition is and why understanding customers is so important. • Uniqueness and Competition analysis; educational information explaining how to identify competitors and how to make unique offer. • Experimenting; educational information explaining why experimenting is important for building a startup. • Minimum Viable Product; educational information helping a startup to understand the most important parts of building MVP and how true to the final product it should be. 			

- Effective Planning; educational information about effective planning techniques and how to manage priorities.

After watching this week's videos participants will learn:

- How to develop a value proposition.
- How to make a unique offer that sets a startup apart from the competitors.
- How to experiment to test assumptions about product, business, customers early and pivot if needed.
- How to build or update the MVP development plan.
- How to effectively plan and prioritize the product development.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 4 “PRODUCT AND PLANNING” ASSIGNMENTS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	May 2024, Programme Week 4		

This week's assignments are:

- Discovery Interviews; template provided with guiding questions on how to understand potential customer problems and how to successfully conduct customer interviews.
- MVP and Product development Plan; document provided with guiding questions and advice on how to plan MVP, how to understand what’s important and what’s not.
- Effective planning; document provided with guiding questions and advice on how to manage OKRs.

WEEK 5

Table 10 Weekly Overview – Week 5

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 5: “STAYING STRONG” WEBINAR “PITCHING”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 5		

This session is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead and invited speakers using Zoom video call platform. The goal of this session is to explain to participants how to build a pitch deck and prepare a 3-minute investor pitch of their deep tech startup for investors. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from participants. After the session, participants will:

- Learn how to build pitch deck slides.
- Learn how to create 3 min pitch speech.
- See good and bad examples of pitch slides.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 5: "STAYING STRONG" PEER TO PEER "LIFE HACKS"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 5		
<p>The goal of this session is to give participants an opportunity to discuss "Life hacks" that startups use to perform better and develop their business as well as their personal lives to keep optimal energy. All the participants have access to the Peer-to-Peer session's instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session's topic.</p>			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 5: "STAYING STRONG" WEBINAR "DEEP-TECH PROJECT AND TIME MANAGEMENT"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 5		
<p>The goal of this session is to address and discuss what difficulties are facing women when building deep tech startups and other complex tech solutions especially from planning processes and managing team point of view including time management, have role models speakers that can share positive examples, and discuss technological aspects of building deep tech products. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from participants. After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive support on how to efficiently plan the project and time for building their deep tech complex solutions; • Hear role models and positive examples of women building deep tech products; 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 5: "STAYING STRONG" VIDEO MATERIALS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 5		
<p>Week 5: This week's focus is on how to stay on top of your game to push the startup to the next level.</p> <p>Videos to watch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimal Energy; educational information on how to apply PERFORM methodology and stay mentally and physically strong • Staying focused; educational information about how to stay focused and do the right thing that will bring success • Founders Roles & Responsibilities; 2 educational videos explaining what a startup founder role and responsibilities should be • How To Talk About The Product...In Times of Crisis; educational information about what a startup founder should do or say in times of crisis 			

- Crisis Management; educational information on how to approach a team in a time of crisis and build a strong culture that can pass through any storm

After watching this week's videos participants will learn:

- How to stay mentally and physically strong and maintain balanced energy distribution
- How to plan effectively and set priorities that help a startup to grow
- What startup founder should do and what not being in this role
- How to communicate with external resources, customers about the product in a time of crisis
- How to manage the team spirit, build a strong culture and stay on a top of the game in the time of crisis

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 5: "STAYING STRONG" ASSIGNMENTS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 5		

This week's assignments are:

- Optimal energy; template provided with instructions and task to understand better where the energy has been spent and if there is a healthy balance.
- Restaurant activity; template provided with a task to create a restaurant that actually represents a startup. All team members have been asked to do the task to see if the team is aligned at the most important aspects of the business.
- Crisis planning; template provided asking a startup to create a core plan in case crisis arise.

WEEK 6

Table 1 Weekly Overview – Week 6

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 6: "SALES" Q&A SESSION "SETTING GOALS CHECK"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 6		

The goal of this session is to check on the progress of reaching the goals that were set at the beginning of the programme and provide practical advice in case any of the startups would experience difficulties with reaching the goals. All the participants have a chance to ask questions and receive guidance and/or advice. This session is 2 hours.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 6: "SALES" Q&A SESSION "SALES"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 6		
<p>The objective of this session is to discuss the Sales topic, the invited sales expert will answer participants' questions regarding sales and will support them by giving best practices and techniques. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from the participants. After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what the best practices and sales techniques are used when making sales; • Ask questions and receive support about your startup related to sales topics; 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 6: "SALES" PEER TO PEER SESSION "BRAND"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 6		
<p>The goal of this session is to give participants an opportunity to discuss their brands - what impression other participants have when looking at their deep tech startup brand, what color combinations are used in design and website, what logo represents, and other related questions. All the participants have access to the Peer-to-Peer session's instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session's topic.</p>			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 6: "SALES" FIRESIDE CHAT "WOMEN JOURNEY IN DEEP TECH INDUSTRY"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 6		
<p>The goal of this session is to listen to stories of deep tech female-led startups, the role models for our participants who can share their journey of starting and growing a deep tech startup. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from participants. After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn how invited female founders launched their deep tech business; • Get inspired and learn more about the ups and downs of this journey; • Ask any related questions they may have; 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 6: "SALES" VIDEO MATERIALS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 6		
<p>Week 6: This week's focus is on sales and how to make sure that the brand sets the startup apart from everyone else.</p> <p>Videos to watch:</p>			

- Idea validation & traction; educational information to help a startup understand how to move to the next level and have traction.
- Leverage your network; educational information with practical advice on how to find new leads.
- How to reach out to contacts; educational information with practical advice on how to reach out to the potential customers.
- Brand: The basics; educational information with practical advice on how to develop a brand that speaks to customers

After watching this week's videos participants will learn:

- How to validate idea and get the traction
- How to and from where to get contact information about the potential customers.
- The best practices on how to reach out to the potential customers.
- How to develop a brand that stands out and really represents a startup purpose and values

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 6: "SALES" ASSIGNMENTS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 6		

This week's assignments are:

- Idea validation and traction; template provided that will help startup to create a sales pipeline and understand better sales goals.
- How to leverage your network; document provided with a step-by-step guide on how to quickly find people who can be reached out directly
- How to reach out to contacts; template provided to help a startup to create a customer reach-out strategy.
- Minimum viable brand; document provided with guiding questions and a task to help distinguish from competitors and create an outstanding brand.
- A rose by any other name; document provided with instructions and a task on how to ensure that startup brand name is unique.

WEEK 7

Table 12 Weekly Overview – Week 7

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 7 "FUNDRAISING" Q&A SESSION "FUNDRAISING"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 7		

The objective of this session is to discuss the Fundraising topic, the invited Fundraising expert will answer participants' questions regarding investments and will support them by giving best practices and techniques. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from the participants. Learn how to build pitch deck slides. After the session, participants will:

- Understand what the best fundraising practices are.
- Ask questions and receive support about your startup related to fundraising topics.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 7: "FUNDRAISING" PEER TO PEER SESSION "COMMUNICATION"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 7
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The goal of this session is to give participants an opportunity to discuss how to communicate effectively and share current challenges in communication with the startup and external resources would be customers, investors, or collaborators.

All the participants have access to the Peer-to-Peer session's instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session's topic.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 7 "FUNDRAISING" PITCH DRILLS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 7
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This session is held online with all participants together with the invited expert and Programme Lead using Zoom video call platform. However, this time each startup has their individual time slot to present their 3 min investor pitch with slides and then receive individual feedback and suggestions. Other startups can join to listen and learn from others' mistakes and best practices. This is a mandatory session in order to later be selected for Progress Day presentations.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 7 "FUNDRAISING" VIDEO MATERIALS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 7
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Week 7: This week's focus is on robust communication.

Videos to watch:

- Leadership Communication; educational information on how to effectively communicate with partners, colleagues and a team.
- Communication Basics Robust; educational information about how to engage with a team.
- Providing Feedback; educational information with practical advice on providing feedback techniques

- Receiving Feedback; educational information with practical advice on receiving feedback techniques
- Holistic Strategy; educational information on how to measure and comprehend how employees are experiencing the company.
- Never Enough; educational information on how to understand what is important for future success and people growth.
- Startup Finance; educational information about how to create a financial plan and which are the most important points.
- SaaS Metrics; educational information on how to understand customer acquisition costs, customer lifetime value, and churn rates.

After watching this week's videos participants will learn:

- Effective communication methods.
- How to engage with a team and create a motivational work environment.
- Why it is important to provide feedback and the best methods how to do that.
- Why it is important to receive feedback and the best methods how to do that.
- How to understand how employees are experiencing the company and whether some changes have to be made.
- How to take care of a startup and people future growth.
- How to create a financial plan and understand where the money is coming from and where it is going to ensure that a startup has a solid runway.
- How to understand the real cost of running the business beyond the salaries and infrastructure so that it is easier for investors to evaluate the startup's business viability.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 7 "FUNDRAISING" ASSIGNMENTS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	June 2024, Programme Week 7		

This week's assignments are:

- Financial plan; template provided, and a startup has been asked to create a financial plan
- Finances; template provided with a task for a startup to brainstorm where money is going to and coming from.

WEEK 8

Table 13 Weekly Overview – Week 8

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 8: "LEGAL" Q&A SESSION "LEGAL"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	July 2024, Programme Week 8		
<p>The objective of this session is to discuss the Legal topic, the invited Legal expert will answer participants' questions regarding legal documents, GDPR, IP and other legal related. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from the participants. This session is 1-2 hours long depending on the number of questions from the participants. After the session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about most important legal documents that every startup should have; • Understand the basics of GDPR; • Can ask any related questions to legal topics. 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 8: "LEGAL" VIDEO MATERIALS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	July 2024, Programme Week 8		
<p>Week 8: This week's focus is on understanding legal, GDPR, and IP basics. Videos to watch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Term Sheets; educational information about what is a term sheet, and why it is needed. • Registering Your Business; educational information about how to decide where to register a legal entity. • Basics of GDPR; educational information about the GDPR and why it is important to think on data protection. • Knowing Your IP: Introduction; educational information about what is IP and why it is important to understand which parts of your business can be protected. • Protecting Your IP; educational information with practical advice on how to the IP audit in a company • How To Deal with Lawyers; educational information on how to work with lawyers. <p>After watching this week's videos participants will learn:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is a term sheet and why it is important to have it. Also, what is valuation, liquidation preferences, vesting, options, anti-dilution, pro-rata rights, and how to have control of a startup. • Why it is important to choose the right country for a startup business where to register it. • How GDPR impacts a business and why it is important to think about it in already early-stage • How to understand what IP in a company is and how to protect it. • How to work with lawyers when you are a startup and not to overspend when dealing with legal matters. 			

ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRAMME WEEK 8: "LEGAL" ASSIGNMENTS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	July 2024, Programme Week 8		
<p>This week's assignments are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR Mapping Your Data Guidelines; template provided with instructions to understand data assets. • GDPR Mapping Template; template provided to fill it in and to understand how to protect data. • Termsheet; document provided with guiding questions and a task to understand how to prepare for future negotiations with investors. • Final version of the 3 min investor pitch deck (this task is mandatory); startups have to submit their recorded 3 min investor pitch deck. 			
ACTIVITY TYPE	KPIS AND GOALS CHECK IN 1ON1 SESSIONS "PROGRESS"	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	July 2024, Programme Week 8		
<p>This session is held online individually with every startup between participants from a specific startup and Programme Lead or Lead Coach using Zoom video call platform or Google Meets.</p> <p>The goal of these individual calls is to have dedicated time for every startup to check how they are progressing with their Programme and company Goals and KPIs that were set at the beginning of the programme. This session is 30-60 min long depending on the number of questions from the participant.</p> <p>Depending on the progress of participants they can continue the Programme and pitch on the Progress Day or have discussion about their participation.</p>			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PROGRESS DAY	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG & BAE
TIMELINE	July 2024, Programme Week 8		
<p>This session is held online via Zoom video conferencing platform, with all participants together, Program partners and Program Lead, also program mentors and Coaches can be invited. The session is 2-3 hours long depending on how many participants will pitch.</p> <p>Progress Day's main goal is to see what the startups have learned during the 8 weeks and to present a 3 min investor pitch to the audience online.</p> <p>After the Progress Day, the startups will have August off to go over the available online content and to prepare for Part 2 which will be with a focus on Investor readiness and will last 10 weeks.</p>			

3.2 EmpoWOMEN programme PART 2

Part Two of the programme will be delivered by Business Angels Europe (BAE) and will be led by Jenny Tooth OBE, VP Diversity at BAE and CEO of UK Business Angels Association and who is a leading expert in gender focused investing together with Reginald Vossen, President of BAE and CEO Ban Flanders who also developed the Women Wise Academy focused on educating women entrepreneurs seeking investment.

The purpose of this 10-week programme will be to provide an in-depth understanding of how to successfully prepare and position the deep tech business for attracting investment. This second part of the programme is designed to build on the learnings gained during the first part focusing on business development to complement the course content and mentoring provided through part one.

The course will cover the topics as set out below, providing insight on how to develop an effective strategy to approach investing both for women who are approaching funding for the first time and enable them to build upon any existing experience they have had in seeking funding to date. Each module will be designed to take the entrepreneurs through each step of the investment process, from developing an effective investment proposal and investment toolkit, successful pitching, follow up engagement with investors, preparing for the due diligence process, investor negotiation including valuation, also providing extensive insight into the legal and contractual process, including deal structuring whilst also enabling insight into their relationship with the investors post deal, governance and strategic planning for future funding rounds.

The weekly Modules will be presented in the form of a live webinar enabling direct learning and engagement whilst enabling immediate Q&A opportunities to discuss any specific aspects with the tutors.

The webinars will be delivered by highly experienced Angel investors selected from BAE's own membership who are all established Angel investors in startups and early-stage businesses, many with deep domain experience in technology including deep tech and key relevant sector application. A significant proportion of the Angel tutors will be Women Angel investors who will be drawn from BAE's Women Angel Leaders Task force. They will give deep insights into the potential challenges and issues encountered by women in deep tech and recognising their specific concerns in seeking funding. In addition, we will be drawing on Legal experts to deliver the Webinar on legal and contractual documents and technical insights.

A key element of the design of this programme and that differentiates it from other similar programmes is providing extensive insights and understanding among the women entrepreneurs of how investors think and approach the investments they make this gives specific understanding of how to approach and engage

investors understanding their requirements and needs for information and how to effectively work with them to achieve a successful outcome.

Each webinar will be recorded so that the entrepreneurs can access the webinar at any time in a recorded version and this will also include access to additional materials, templates, links and further tools and resources which will be made available online through the MPO platform. Each webinar will be accompanied by a knowledge test which the female entrepreneur will be asked to complete which enables them to check their understanding and learning and go back to key elements in the webinar to reinforce their knowledge and understanding. The entrepreneur will be supported throughout by their SWG coach or mentor who will help to reinforce their understanding and address any issues raised in the programme modules or content.

The programme will culminate in the Demo day which will be jointly organised by SWG and BAE, where the skills and knowledge gained by the women in deep tech across both parts of the programme will be demonstrated and enabling feedback and advice from both investors, mentors, and coaches.

Table 14 Programme Part 2 by Week

WEEK	DESCRIPTION
WEEK 1 FUNDRAISING STRATEGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the Investment Market and equity supply chain -what finance is right for you; • What are Business Angels, angel syndicates and their added value • Identifying your funding strategy from Angel to Scale-up
WEEK 2 INVESTMENT PROPOSAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do Investors Look for in a Deep tech Business. • Understanding the core elements of your Deep tech Investment proposal to present to investors.
WEEK 3 INVESTMENT FINANCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing your investment proposition and financials. • Establishing your investment needs.
WEEK 4 INVESTORS TOOLKIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing Your Toolkit to Attract Investors
WEEK 5 PITCHING TO INVESTORS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making a winning Pitch; • Core elements to cover; • Style and presentation skills; Telling your story- why you.

WEEK	DESCRIPTION
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engaging with investors after the pitch Preparing for Due Diligence; scope and purpose and how to respond to investors needs
WEEK 6 NEGOTIATIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding how to value your business – art or science? How to negotiate and understand what investors require. The right deal structure; equity ; Convertible loans and ASA
WEEK 7 TERM SHEETS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the key elements of the Term Sheet and finalising the deal. What can go wrong and when to walk away
WEEK 8 LEGAL PROCESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal processes – understanding the core documents. Shareholders Agreement and Articles of Association
WEEK 9 POST INVESTMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the Cap table Signing and closing the deal. Making the most of your investors post investment
WEEK 10 GRADUATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demo day presentations to investors and audience.

SUMMER BREAK ACTIVITIES

Table 15 Weekly Overview – Summer Break

ACTIVITY TYPE	AUGUST TASKS BY BAE FOR SUMMER BREAK	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	July 2024, Programme Week 8		
<p>Over the August period and to maintain momentum, cohort participants will be assigned the following tasks to complete during the interim. Between the end of the business development part of the programme and the investment readiness.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing your finance and investment plan - Consider your current finances and how much investment or external funding you will require to move your business to the next stage consider key aspects such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> further team hiring 			

- market development
- technology and IP development
- hardware
- wider business costs
- other finance needs
- **Raising finance- lessons learned so far from raising finance** - Consider what you have learned so far: set out the challenges/barriers you encountered and benefits from any funding you have raised (debt, equity or grants) ; what tips would you pass on to other Women in deeptech from your experiences.

WEEK 10

Table 16 Weekly Overview – Week 10

ACTIVITY TYPE	PEER TO PEER SESSION “WELCOME BACK”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	September 2024, Programme Week 10		
<p>The objective of this session is to discuss the progress made during the summer break and to address the significant challenges faced in attracting investment.</p> <p>All the participants have access to the Peer to Peer session’s instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session’s topic.</p>			

WEEK 13

Table 17 Weekly Overview – Week 13

ACTIVITY TYPE	INTRODUCTION TO THE INVESTMENT READINESS PROGRAMME	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	September 2024, Programme Week 13		
<p>This session is held online and will be delivered live, led by senior Project representatives of BAE (Jenny Tooth and Reginald Vossen) using Zoom video and will be recorded. It will last up to 1 hour and cover the following topic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the overall investment readiness programme and what will be covered in the weeks ahead. This will include considerations that they may want to make about their own business and finance needs which will be based on the task that they have carried out during the August break on that finance plan and needs – and consideration of their experiences and lessons learned so far. 			

- The session will include an opportunity for participants to ask questions about the Investment readiness programme and to each say a little about their Fundraising experience so far challenges and successes (reflection on what they have learned so far).

ACTIVITY TYPE	INVESTMENT READINESS “THE CORE BASICS”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
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TIMELINE	September 2024, Programme Week 13
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This session is held online and will be delivered live by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded and will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:

- Understanding the Investment Market and equity supply chain -what finance is right for you.
- What are Business Angels, angel syndicates and their added value.
- Identifying your funding strategy from Angel to Scale-up.

This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples, and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur. The session aims:

This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of the overall funding landscape and Investment market; what are the different areas of finance that are right for your business and stage of development; developing the core elements of a funding plan and strategy. The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last up to 30 minutes.

This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PEER TO PEER SESSION “BUILDING CREDIBILITY IN MALE DOMINATED INDUSTRY ”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
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TIMELINE	September 2024, Programme Week 13
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The objective of this session is to explore strategies for building self-confidence and credibility as a female founder in the male-dominated deep tech industry.

WEEK 14

Table 18 Weekly Overview – Week 14

ACTIVITY TYPE	UNDERSTANDING THE NEEDS AND REQUIREMENTS OF INVESTORS AND HOW	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
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	TO DEVELOP AN EFFECTIVE INVESTMENT PROPOSAL		
TIMELINE	September 2024, Programme Week 14		
<p>This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do Investors Look for in a Deep tech Business. • Understanding the core elements of your Deep tech Investment proposal to present to investors – innovation; technology; growth strategy; Defensible IP <p>The session aims:</p> <p>This will be designed to enable an in depth understanding of how investors will evaluate an investment opportunity from a deep tech business. This will also aim to give an in depth insight of some of the challenges and barriers that they may experience as a woman LED deep tech business and how to develop a clear investment opportunity that indicates their strengths and potential and which may overcome any potential gender bias. Notably they will re they have an opportunity to understand the thinking of an investor and how they will approach key elements of their investment proposal what they will need to consider and think about when presenting to investors the kinds of areas that they will particularly look at from both the innovation product to the sector application to their market growth strategy and building a defensible competitive position.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will last up to 30 minutes.</p> <p>This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.</p>			
ACTIVITY TYPE	MENTOR DAY	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	October 2024, Programme Week 13		
<p>This session is held online using Zoom platform. Before the session startups will choose up to 4 mentors from provided 20+ mentors and on a Mentor Day will have individual 1on1 sessions in Zoom breakout rooms with each of the selected mentors. Duration of each session is 45 minutes long.</p> <p>During the session:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Startup will ask the questions. • Mentor will answer the questions and provide feedback and expertise on the subject. • Mentor will advise on any next steps or best practices that the startup should follow. <p>The Mentor Day is managed by Mentor Day manager who will also moderate the session.</p>			

WEEK 15

Table 19 Weekly Overview – Week 15

ACTIVITY TYPE	IDENTIFYING YOUR INVESTMENT NEEDS AND PRESENTING YOUR INVESTMENT PROPOSAL	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	September 2024, Programme Week 15		
<p>This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing your investment proposition and financials • Establishing and presenting your investment needs <p>The session aims:</p> <p>This will build on the previous week's session and is designed to enable the participants to build their skills in developing an effective proposition that sets out a clear investment level financial projections based on a clear understanding of their business growth strategy, their traction achieved so far and understanding their finance needs. The aim will be to provide clear insights on how to move from a business plan to an investment plan and gaining an in depth understanding of how investors will evaluate financial projections and their financial needs as a deep tech business and what they will need to consider and think about when presenting to investors.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will last up to 30 minutes.</p> <p>This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.</p>			
ACTIVITY TYPE	DEVELOPING YOUR INVESTMENT READINESS TOOLKIT	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	October 2024, Programme Week 15		
<p>This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing Your Toolkit to Attract Investors • What data and information investors want to see. <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples, and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur.</p>			

The session aims:

This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to develop an effective and comprehensive Toolkit to meet the requirements of investors and prepare for direct engagement with investors. The toolkit will include the financial plan and proposition; executive summary; pitch presentation short and long); other data and documentary requirements to address investors information needs. Each element will be carefully defined and explained and with relevant examples for women in deeptech.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will last up to 30 minutes.

This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.

WEEK 16

Table 20 Weekly Overview– Week 16

ACTIVITY TYPE	MAKING A WINNING PITCH AND HOW TO DEVELOP YOUR SKILLS IN ENGAGING WITH INVESTORS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	October 2024, Programme Week 16		
<p>This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making your Winning Pitch to Investors • Successful presentation skills • Engaging with investors <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples, and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur.</p> <p>The session aims:</p> <p>This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to develop an effective and comprehensive Toolkit to meet the requirements of investors and prepare for direct engagement with investors. The toolkit will include the financial plan and proposition; executive summary; pitch presentation short and long); other data and documentary requirements to address investors’ information needs. Each element will be carefully defined and explained and with relevant examples for women in deeptech.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A</p>			

online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will last up to 30 minutes.

This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.

ACTIVITY TYPE	PEER TO PEER SESSION “FINANCIAL LITERACY AND FUNDING STRATEGIES”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	October 2024, Programme Week 16		

This session is held online with all participants together with the Programme Lead using Zoom video call platform. The goal of this session is to facilitate a discussion and exchange of ideas on how peers are creating financial concepts and developing effective funding strategies for deep tech startups.

All the participants have access to the Peer-to-Peer session’s instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session’s topic.

WEEK 17

Table 21 Weekly Overview – Week 17

ACTIVITY TYPE	POST PITCH PREPARING FOR DUE DILIGENCE	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	October 2024, Programme Week 17		

This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:

- Post Pitch Follow up with Investors.
- Preparing for Detailed Due Diligence.

This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples, and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur.

The session aims:

This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to engage with investors in the period following the pitching session. It will aim to provide clear understanding of how to effectively follow up with investors following the pitching session and to ensure investor interest.

The second half of this session will be designed to give an in depth understanding of how to prepare for and engage in the due diligence process. This will include understanding the core elements of the business and investment proposition that will be looked at in depth and ensuring that they have gathered all of the

relevant data evidence and information to address the investor’s concerns and issues in a timely and effective and confident way. It will include an understanding of how investors conduct due diligence particularly at Angel and early stage investment level and their approach to the five core areas: the founders and team; the business model; the market; the technology product and applications; the corporate structure; the legal issues and the financials. Illustrations will be given of the information formats and presentations of how to approach the detailed and in depth questioning and inquiries and ensure that they are well prepared for the process also understanding the opportunity to gain more in-depth insight into the investors themselves and whether this is likely to be a successful and valuable relationship.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will last up to 30 minutes.

This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.

WEEK 18

Table 22 Weekly Overview– Week 18

ACTIVITY TYPE	HOW TO VALUE YOUR DEEP TECH BUSINESS AND NEGOTIATE WITH INVESTORS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	October 2024, Programme Week 18		
<p>This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding how to value your business- Art or Science? • Understanding potential deal structures and; • How to effectively negotiation and understand what investors require and what works for you. <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples, and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur.</p> <p>The session aims:</p> <p>This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to value your business for investment purposes and how to understand the approach that investors are likely to make in understanding the valuation of your business and the methodologies that can be applied and that this frequently more of an art than a science and the importance of creating a flexible approach to negotiation. The session will be devised to provide practical understanding and parameters for valuation in relation to an early stage scaling deep tech business, whilst having a clear understanding of the approach and requirements of investors including exemplars, case studies and practical tips on how to justify and present</p>			

the valuation to the investor, whilst understanding the points of negotiation and conflict.

A final aspect of this session will be to gain an overall understanding of how to approach the structure of the deal in relation to the valuation and finance needs and the benefits of both direct equity deals , or those based on convertible loan notes and advanced security mechanisms that establish the valuation over a period of time the benefits and the negatives of the different approaches in the context a valuation and successfully accessing investment.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will last up to 30 minutes.

This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.

ACTIVITY TYPE	UNDERSTANDING THE TERMSHEET AND ACHIEVING A SUCCESSFUL OUTCOME	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	November 2024, Programme Week 18		

This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:

- Understanding the Key elements of the Termsheet
- What can go wrong with the deal.

This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples, and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur.

The session aims:

This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to engage with investors in order to achieve a Termsheet as an indication of the commitment to make an investment and how to successfully manage the negotiation process. The aim of the session will be to give an in depth understanding of the key terms of the timesheet and how this relates to the due diligence process, building on the previous session; how to respond to the details information and evidence requirements to ensure that investors are satisfied; providing a clear understanding of some of the pitfalls and challenges in achieving a successful and satisfactory timesheet. Notably, this session will aim to equip the women in deep tech with a clear understanding of how to confidently negotiate, work with and gain the outcome of the type of investment and level of investment they require, whilst at the same time understanding that the process may breakdown and their opportunities to walk away from the process if this does not feel right.

The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will last up to 30 minutes.

This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links;

additional data; case studies; templates.			
ACTIVITY TYPE	PEER TO PEER SESSION “NEGOTIATION AND DEAL-MAKING”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	October 2024, Programme Week 18		
<p>The goal of this session is to discuss techniques for successful negotiation and deal-making in the context of deep tech startups. All the participants have access to the Peer to Peer session’s instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session’s topic.</p>			

WEEK 19

Table 23 Weekly Overview – Week 19

ACTIVITY TYPE	UNDERSTANDING THE LEGAL CONTRACTUAL PROCESS AND DOCUMENTATION TO STRUCTURE THE DEAL	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	November 2024, Programme Week 19		
<p>This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the Legal Process and the Core Documents • The Shareholders Agreement • Articles of Association. <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples, and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur.</p> <p>The session aims:</p> <p>This session will be designed to give an in-depth understanding of the legal and contractual aspects of closing the deal, providing a detailed understanding of the core documents; what the various terms and requirements mean; and that the contractual requirements and protections are clearly understood. It will aim to provide understanding of what is their relationship to the investors post investment, the protections on both sides and ensure that they are confident in their knowledge of the relevant documentation and technical aspects.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will last up to 30 minutes.</p> <p>This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their</p>			

own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.

WEEK 20

Table 24 Weekly Overview – Week 20

ACTIVITY TYPE	FINALISING THE DEAL	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	November 2024, Programme Week 20		
<p>This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalizing the investment deal. • Understanding the Cap table. • Governance and Reporting. <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples, and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur.</p> <p>The session aims:</p> <p>This session will build on the previous session on legal documents and focuses on closing the deal. It will be designed to cover the final elements of consideration, both contractually and in terms of the ongoing relationship with investors and why these areas are important for the ongoing relationship between the women in deep tech team and their investors and for the future development of their business. This will include understanding the Capital table as a core component of the final Shareholders agreement and sets out the number of shares that by the founders and other existing investors in the business and the shares that will be held by new investors and why this is important for ongoing control and incentives for the founders and team. The session will also talk about the key areas in the shareholders agreement about Governance and which will set out the investor’s role on the board and what expectations there are of reporting and providing strategic information and why it's important to finalise these issues prior to closing the deal.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will last up to 30 minutes.</p> <p>This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.</p>			

ACTIVITY TYPE	PEER TO PEER SESSION “CULTIVATING LEADERSHIP SKILLS”	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG
TIMELINE	October 2024, Programme Week 18		
<p>The goal of this session is to discuss techniques for developing leadership skills and strategies to effectively lead a deep tech startup.</p> <p>All the participants have access to the Peer-to-Peer session’s instructions in PDF format including a description of how the session will be conducted along with questions to be asked and discussed related to the exact session’s topic.</p>			

WEEK 21

Table 25 Weekly Overview – Week 21

ACTIVITY TYPE	MAKING THE MOST OF YOUR INVESTORS POST DEAL AND PLANNING FOR NEXT STAGE FUNDING	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	BAE
TIMELINE	November 2024, Programme Week 20		
<p>This session is held online and will be delivered live led by an Experienced Angel Investor using Zoom video call and will be recorded. It will last 2 hours. It will cover the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making the most of your investors post investment. • Planning further funding rounds. <p>This will include a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples, and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur.</p> <p>The session aims:</p> <p>This session will focus on the relationship with investors after the deal is done and will be designed to provide an in depth understanding of how to effectively work with investors to get the most out of their experience, expertise, introductions, knowledge, and support which provides important added value to the business post investment. The session will provide insight and case studies of how to make the investor relationship work effectively -the do's and don'ts of how to work together. A further key part of the session will be to discuss the planning of the next round of investment as the business grows and at what point after the first investment to start to plan for accessing next stage investment; the role of the investor and how to position your business for next stage funding.</p> <p>This will provide a final session on the investment process, before the final Demo day session at the end of the Course when the women entrepreneurs will be engaging with the investors.</p> <p>The webinar will include a structured Q&A session which will both include questions put into the Q&A online, as well as opportunities for direct face to face questions. The Q&A session will last between will</p>			

last up to 30 minutes.

This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.

WEEK 22

Table 26 Weekly Overview – Week 22

ACTIVITY TYPE	FINAL KPIS AND GOALS CHECK IN 1ON1 SESSIONS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG & BAE
TIMELINE	November 2024, Programme Week 22		
<p>This session is held online individually with every startup between participants from a specific startups and Programme Lead or Lead Coach using Zoom video call platform or Google Meets.</p> <p>The goal of these individual calls is to have dedicated time for every startup to check how they are progressing with their Programme and company Goals and KPIs that were set in the beginning.</p> <p>This session is 30-60 min long depending on the number of questions from the participant.</p> <p>Depending on the progress of participants they can be invited to officially graduate from the programme.</p> <p>This will be followed by a short knowledge test available online to be completed by the participants in their own time and which will reference back to the topics and key learning elements. Further learning resources related to the key topics will also be available on the Airtable platform, including wider website links; additional data; case studies; templates.</p>			
ACTIVITY TYPE	DEMO DAY & ENGAGEMENT WITH INVESTORS	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	SWG & BAE
TIMELINE	November 2024, Programme Week TBC		
<p>This session is jointly delivered by SWG and BAE providing opportunities to directly present to investors, alongside other key players from the EMPO Programme partnership. BAE will mobilize a group of investors with core experience and expertise in investing in Deeptech and with a specific focus on involving women Angel investors.</p>			

Annex 1. Programme Booklet

EmpoWomen Programme

Overview

This is 6 months programme which consists of 2 parts:

- **Part 1- How to build and scale** women-led deep tech startup led by Startup Wise Guys (SWG) + Progress Day
- **Part 2 - Investor readiness programme** for women-led deep tech startups led by Business Angels Europe (BAE) and SWG + Graduation Day

Activities

The programme will include the following:

- Pre-recorded videos
- Practical assignments
- Q&A live sessions
- Peer 2 Peer sessions
- Fireside chats
- Webinars
- Mentorship
- 1on1 sessions with batch lead

Focus

Program is ready to be adapted to the needs of selected startups:

- Fireside chats and sessions with Role Models
- Lead coaches that host live Q&As in Part 1 will be female experts
- Workshops focusing on specific startup verticals and current needs
- Individual sessions with mentors that are selected and assigned according to startup vertical and maturity state

Timeline

Programme timeline during 6 months

Programme Flow

Each week consists of the following:

On Fridays new week has been unlocked and we ask startups to:

- Watch videos and take notes (up to an hour a week)
- Participate in the live Q&A sessions (1 to 1.5 hours a week)
- Engage in Peer-to-Peer sessions with other participants (1 hour a week)
- Work on the practical exercises & challenges (2 to 4 hours a week)
- Work on pitch & presentation skills (up to 1 hour)

Some of the exercises can be done individually but for most the whole team is needed. We recommend blocking around 4 hours a week on Mondays or Tuesdays to work on these before the live Q&As and peer-to-peer sessions.

Part 1

How to build and scale women-led deep tech startup led by Startup Wise Guys

Part 1

First part of the programme will last 8 weeks - **How to build and scale women-led deep tech startup led by Startup Wise Guys**

Week 1

Welcome & Goals

Week 2

Purpose and Values

Week 3

Pitching and Product

Week 4

Product and Planning

Week 5

Staying Strong

Week 6

Sales

Week 7

Fundraising

Week 8

Legal basics & Progress day

Week 1

Topic: Welcome & Goals setting

This week is to meet other participants, explore and understand programme flow as well as start planning your deep tech startup goals that you would like to reach during the programme.

Videos

- How does the programme works?
- Mentoring Top 10 tips
- Alumni Testimonials

Practical tasks:

1. Fill in Startup Entry form
2. Add Program's calendar
3. Join Slack
4. Sign up to program's Airtable to get access to the content

Live sessions

- Welcome session
- Programme KPIs and goals
- Peer 2 Peer "Myths and Stereotypes of women-led deep tech startups"

Week 2

Topic: Purpose and Values

Why are you here? What is the purpose of your deep tech startup company? What is your mission, vision, and culture?

Videos

- Goal Setting
- Purpose and Values
- The power of strong culture
- Team is my Army
- Stages of A startup
- Deconstructing your business
- Introduction to pitching

Practical tasks:

1. Set goals for the upcoming 8 weeks
2. What is your purpose
3. Your company's values
4. Lean Canvas exercise
5. Start working on Pitch Deck (template included)

Live sessions

- Goal setting 1on1 with batch lead
- Peer 2 Peer "Purpose and Values for you as founder of a deep-tech female lead startup"

Week 3

Topic: Pitching and Product

Understanding your deep tech product. Learn how to understand why being clear about the problem is the first step to solving (and selling) your product.

Videos

- Problems to solve
- There are No Problems, Only Solutions Waiting to be Found
- How to identify your ideal customer
- Powerful Pitching. The Basics
- Powerful Pitching. The Hook and the product
- Powerful Pitching. The Market, Business, Company
- Powerful Pitching. Summary
- Stage pitch examples

Practical tasks:

1. SWOT analysis
2. Ideal Customer Profile
3. How to build your pitch

Live sessions

- Q&A "Problem Definition"
- Peer 2 Peer "Pitch Practice"

Week 4

Topic: Product and Planning

This week's focus is building a deep tech product - something unique that your customers want.

Videos

- Value proposition
- Uniqueness and Competitor Analysis
- Experimenting
- Minimum Viable Product
- Effective Planning

Practical tasks:

1. Discovery Interviews
2. MVP and Product development Plan
3. Effective planning

Live sessions

- Q&A "MVP & Planning"
- Peer 2 Peer "Tough Questions"
- Webinar "Women and complex tech solutions"

Week 5

Topic: Staying Strong

How can you stay on top of your game to push your deep tech startup to the next level? How to get ready for the next step?

Videos

- Optimal Energy
- Manage Your Time When Everything is Burning
- Founders Roles & Responsibilities
- How To Talk About The Product..In Times of Crisis
- Crisis Management

Practical tasks:

1. Optimal energy
2. Restaurant activity
3. Crisis planning

Live sessions

- Webinar "Pitching"
- Peer 2 Peer "Life Hacks"
- Webinar "Deep-tech Project and Time management"

Week 6

Topic: Sales

This week is an intensive crash course in sales, marketing, and branding for your deep tech startup

Videos

- Idea validation & traction
- Leverage your network
- How to reach out to contacts
- Brand: The basics
- Naming your startup

Practical tasks:

1. Idea validation and traction
2. How to leverage your network
3. How to reach out to contacts
4. Minimum viable brand
5. A rose by any other name

Live sessions

- Q&A "Sales"
- Peer 2 Peer "Brand"
- Fireside chat "Women journey in deep tech industry"

Week 7

Topic: Fundraising

This week, our focus is on enhancing robust communication.

Videos

- Robust Communication: Leadership Communication
- Robust Communication: Communication Basics
- Robust Communication: Providing Feedback
- Robust Communication: Receiving Feedback
- Robust Communication: Holistic Strategy
- Robust Communication: Never Enough
- Startup Finance
- SaaS Metrics

Practical exercises:

1. Financial plan template
2. Finances

Live sessions

- Q&A "Fundraising"
- Peer 2 Peer "Communication"
- Pitch Drills

Week 8

Topic: Legal basics

This week, we're diving into legal matters. We'll discuss essential topics such as where to register your business, GDPR basics, and strategies to avoid legal complexities.

Videos

- Term Sheets
- Registering Your Business
- Basics of GDPR
- Knowing Your IP: Introduction
- Protecting Your IP
- How To Deal With Lawyers

Practical tasks:

1. GDPR Mapping Your Data Guidelines
2. GDPR Mapping Template
3. Final version of the 3 min investor pitch deck

Live sessions

- Q&A "Legal"
- KPIs and Goals check in 1on1 with batch lead

Progress Day

End of Part 1

- Progress Day's main goal is to see what you've learned during the 8 weeks and to present your 3 min investor pitch to the audience online.
- After the Progress Day you will have August off to go over the available online content and to prepare for the Part 2 which will be with a focus on Investor readiness and will last 10 weeks.

Part 2

Investorreadiness programme for women in deep tech seeking to increase their opportunity to raise investment led by Business Angels Europe BAE

Overview

Investor readiness programme for women-led deep tech startups led by BAE

Investor readiness gives you the chance to really understand the investment process in detail and the mindset of investors and how to engage with investors and successfully navigate your investment journey.

While BAE will lead most of the sessions, the Startup Wise Guys team will support overall flow of the programme and also organize additional sessions.

Live sessions

- Webinars delivered by Angel and early stage investors
- Direct Engagement with investors related to your Deep tech sector
- Access to BAE transnational pitching events
- 1on1 with batch lead by SWG
- Peer2Peer sessions by SWG
- Mentor Days (individual mentoring sessions) by SWG

Part 2

Second part is 10 weeks dedicated to **Investor readiness programme for women in deep tech seeking to increase their opportunity to raise investment** led by Business Angels Europe BAE

Week 1

Fundraising strategy

Week 2

Investment proposal

Week 3

Investment finances

Week 4

Investor toolkit

Week 5

Pitching to investors

Week 6

Negotiations

Week 7

Term Sheets

Week 8

Legal processes

Week 9

Post investment

Week 10

Graduation

Week 1

Topics

- Understanding the Investment Market and equity supply chain -what finance is right for you
- What are Business Angels, angel syndicates and their added value
- Identifying your funding strategy from Angel to Scale-up

Week 2

Topics

- What do Investors Look for in a Deep tech Business
- Understanding the core elements of your Deep tech Investment proposal to present to investors – innovation ; technology ; growth strategy; Defensible IP

Week 3

Topics

- Developing your Investment proposition and financials
- Convertible Loans and ASAs
- Establishing your investment needs

Week 4

Topics

- Developing Your Toolkit to Attract Investors
- What data and information investors want to see

Week 5

Topics

- Making a winning Pitch
- Core elements to cover; Style and presentation skills; Telling your story- why you
- Engaging with investors after the pitch
- Preparing for Due Diligence ; scope and purpose and how to respond to investors needs

Week 6

Topics

- Understanding how to value your business – art or science?
- How to negotiate and understand what investors require

Week 7

Topics

- Understanding the key elements of the Term Sheet and finalising the deal
- What can go wrong and when to walk away

Week 8

Topics

- Legal processes – understanding the core documents
- Shareholders Agreement
- Articles of Association
- Understanding Cap table
- Governance and reporting
- Signing and closing the deal

Week 9

Topics

- Making the most of your investors post investment
- How your investors can bring added value added value
- Keeping your investors informed and happy
- Planning further Funding Rounds

Week 10

Graduation Day and End of the programme

- Graduation Day will happen onsite and location will be announced later
- On the Graduation Day you will need to pitch again in front of the audience